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Abstract:

Background: Epilepsy is a common neurological disorder characterized by recurrent seizures due to abnormal neuronal electrical activity. This condition affects approximately 65 million people globally, with around 80% in developing countries. In India, the prevalence ranges from 5.59 to 10 per 1,000 people, with rural areas exhibiting higher rates than urban ones. Epilepsy's impact on cognitive functions, including semantic memory, is significant but often underexplored.

Objective: This study is aimed to assess semantic memory impairment in patients with epilepsy.

Methods: This is a cross-sectional analytical study conducted among 250 epilepsy patients attending the neurology department of a tertiary care centre. The sample was derived based on statistical calculations to ensure sufficient power and accuracy. Inclusion criteria were patients aged over 18 with a diagnosis of epilepsy, while those with intellectual disabilities or neurodegenerative disorders were excluded. Data collection included seizure onset age, seizure semiology, epilepsy duration, antiepileptic drug (AED) use, and MRI and EEG results. Semantic memory was evaluated using the Indian Semantic Memory Test Battery, encompassing naming tests, word-picture matching, and sorting tasks. Statistical analysis involved multivariate regression to examine relationships between cognitive scores and clinical variables.

Results: Among the 250 participants, 147 (59%) had generalized epilepsy and 103 (41%) had focal epilepsy. Sociodemographic factors, clinical profiles, and memory test scores were analyzed. Significant findings included higher rates of MRI abnormalities and EEG changes in focal epilepsy. Semantic memory deficits were evident across all categories. For instance, 10% of generalized epilepsy and 12% of focal epilepsy patients scored below 50% in total naming scores. Additionally, significant impairments were observed in word-picture matching and sorting tasks, with overall percentages ranging from 11% to 25.3% for various test levels.

Conclusion: The study highlights that semantic memory impairment in epilepsy extend beyond episodic memory issues, affecting the semantic-verbal system and influencing both memory and language performance. These findings underscore the need for a deeper understanding of semantic processing challenges in epilepsy, which could improve patient care and support. Differentiating between semantic-verbal system impairment and episodic memory deficit is crucial for developing effective therapeutic strategies.

Keywords: epilepsy, semantic memory, focal and generalized epilepsy.

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Introduction

Epilepsy was conceptually defined in 2005 as a brain disorder marked by a lasting tendency to generate epileptic seizures. In practice, this is often applied to individuals who have experienced two or more unprovoked seizures occurring more than 24 hours apart. Epilepsy is a prevalent medical condition that has profound psychological and emotional effects on both patients and their caregivers. Globally, around 65 million people live with epilepsy, with roughly 80% residing in developing countries, where the incidence of new cases ranges from 40 to 70 per 100,000 people. [1] In India, epilepsy affects between 5.59 and 10 per 1,000 individuals, meaning that over 10 million people in the country live

with the condition, comprising more than 1% of the population. The prevalence is higher in rural areas (1.9%) compared to urban areas (0.6%). [2] Epilepsy is a neurological disorder caused by abnormal bursts of electrical activity in certain neurons, which may sometimes spread throughout the brain. This irregular neural activity can lead to cognitive and behavioral changes [3]. The clinical manifestations and outcomes of epilepsy vary depending on the underlying mechanisms. While most individuals with epilepsy have normal intelligence, they are at greater risk of cognitive impairment compared to healthy peers of the same age and educational background. The nature of cognitive deficits often

depends on the specific type of epilepsy. For example, temporal lobe epilepsy (TLE) is frequently linked with memory problems, while focal epilepsy in the language-dominant hemisphere may result in word-finding and naming difficulties. Some epilepsy syndromes are also associated with more severe cognitive or behavioral challenges. [4,5] Memory, a key cognitive function, involves the processes of acquiring, storing, and retrieving information. Acquisition, or encoding, converts physical information into a mental representation, and can vary from processing sensory details to abstract concepts. Storage refers to the retention of encoded information over time, while retrieval involves accessing and extracting stored information from various memory systems. [6]

Semantic memory relates to knowledge about the world, including word meanings, facts, and ideas. It organizes mental knowledge of words and symbols, their meanings, and the relationships between them, making it crucial for language and reasoning. Although impairments in episodic memory are the most recognized cognitive deficits in epilepsy patients, recent research has highlighted deficits in semantic memory as well. Semantic memory dysfunction can manifest in language difficulties, such as problems with naming, verbal fluency, and recalling remote semantic information, which can affect patients' interactions with their environment. While the Cambridge Semantic Memory Test (CSM) is commonly used to assess this, in our study, we employed the adapted Indian Semantic Memory Test (ISM). [7,8]

Objective: To assess the semantic memory impairment in patients with Epilepsy

Methodology:

This cross sectional study was conducted in the Neurology Department of a tertiary care centre. Patients of more than 18 years of age already diagnosed with epilepsy were included in the study after obtaining informed consent. Patient with intellectual disability, dementia, neurodegenerative

disorders etc., and patients with terminal illness like malignancy, liver failure, and renal failure were excluded from the study.

With reference to a study by Paplikar et al taking expected standard deviation to be 1.6 for category fluency task, with margin of error 0.2, with 80% power and z value as 1.96 for 95% confidence interval the calculated sample size is 249 which is rounded off to 250. $N = \frac{z^2 \sigma^2}{d^2}$

The age of onset of seizures, semiology, duration of illness, AED taken is collected with preformed questionnaire. MRI Brain is taken to rule out any focal abnormalities. EEG is taken for all patients.

Semantic memory is tested using validated tool Indian Semantic Memory Test Battery which includes naming test, word to picture matching task, picture and word sorting task, pointing to description task. Final score of 88 will be calculated

Statistical Analysis:

Data is entered in Microsoft Excel (Windows 10, version 2007) and analysis was done using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) for windows software (trial version 20; SPSS Inc, Chicago). Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation for continuous variables and frequencies and percentages for categorical variable are used. Bar charts and pie charts are used for visual representation of data. To find association between two categorical variables chi square test was used. Level of significance will be set at 0.05.

Results:

A total of 250 epilepsy patient attending a super speciality tertiary care centre were included in the study. Among them 147 (59%) had generalized epilepsy and 103 (41%) had focal epilepsy. Table 1 summarises the sociodemographic factors among both groups of study population.

Table 1: Sociodemographic factors among study population:

Variable	Generalized epilepsy (N=147) (59%)	Focal epilepsy (N = 103) (47%)	Total (N=250)	P value
Age (mean ± SD)	36.5 ± 1.7	37.4 ± 1.5	36.8 ± 1.7	0.458
Gender				
Male	95 (65%)	64 (62%)	159 (64%)	0.652
Female	52 (35%)	39 (38%)	91 (36%)	
Age of onset of seizure (Mean ± SD)	24.3 ± 1.2	25.5 ± 1.4	26.1 ± 1.3	0.721
Duration of epilepsy				
Mean ± SD	12.4 ± 2.1	12.8 ± 2.4	12.5 ± 2.3	0.623
< 5 years	63 (43%)	43 (42%)	105 (42%)	
5 – 10 years	59 (40%)	38 (37%)	98 (39%)	
>10 years	25 (17%)	22 (21%)	47 (19%)	

Table 2: Clinical profile of study population:

Variable	Generalized epilepsy (N=147) (59%)	Focal epilepsy (N = 103) (47%)	Total (N=250)	P value
Drug compliance				
Present	99 (67%)	70 (68%)	169 (68%)	0.711
Absent	48 (33%)	33 (32%)	81 (32%)	
Seizure status				
Controlled	81 (55%)	58 (56%)	139 (56%)	0.678
Uncontrolled	66 (45%)	45 (44%)	111 (44%)	
Drug status				
Monotherapy	62 (42%)	45 (44%)	107 (43%)	0.721
Polytherapy	85 (58%)	58 (56%)	143 (57%)	
MRI abnormality				
Present	25 (17%)	32 (31%)	57 (23%)	0.031
Absent	122 (83%)	71 (69%)	193 (77%)	
EEG changes				
Present	41 (28%)	42 (41%)	83 (33%)	0.001
Absent	106 (72%)	61 (59%)	167 (67%)	

Table 3: Indian semantic memory test battery score in study population:

	Generalized epilepsy (N=147) (Mean ± SD)	Focal epilepsy (N = 103) (Mean ± SD)	Total (N=250) (Mean ± SD)	P value
Mean category fluency score	7.2 ± 5.4	6.5 ± 4.2	7.1 ± 6.3	0.012
Total naming score (Max:88)	81 ± 7.2	78 ± 6.4	80 ± 8.5	0.003
Total word-picture matching score (Max:88)	79 ± 6.1	77 ± 7.2	80 ± 8.8	0.004
Picture sorting level 1 (Max:80)	71 ± 5.1	69 ± 6.5	72 ± 7.4	0.001
Word sorting level 1 (Max:80)	68 ± 4.5	67 ± 5.1	68 ± 6.2	0.001
Picture sorting level 2 (Max:80)	73 ± 3.9	70 ± 3.4	72 ± 5.2	0.001
Word sorting level 2 (Max:80)	70 ± 7.5	69 ± 5.8	71 ± 7.9	0.001
Picture sorting level 3 (Max:176)	142 ± 16.1	135 ± 17.2	136 ± 17.9	0.001
Word sorting level 3 (Max:176)	152 ± 17.3	148 ± 18.4	150 ± 17.6	0.001

Table 4: Indian semantic memory test battery score with percentage of population scoring less than 50% in each category

	Generalized epilepsy (N=147) (Mean ± SD)	Focal epilepsy (N = 103) (Mean ± SD)	Total (N=250) (Mean ± SD)
Total naming score (less than 44)	10%	12%	11%
Total word-picture matching score (less than 44)	14%	16%	15%
Picture sorting level 1 (less than 40)	13%	14%	12.5%
Word sorting level 1 (less than 40)	10.5%	12.4%	11.6%
Picture sorting level 2 (less than 40)	12.5%	13.4%	13.2%
Word sorting level 2 (less than 40)	14.3%	15.4%	14.5%
Picture sorting level 3 (less than 88)	21.5%	24.4%	23.6%
Word sorting level 3 (less than 88)	23.3%	25.3%	22.6%

The study population consisted of 250 participants, with 147 (59%) diagnosed with generalized epilepsy and 103 (47%) with focal epilepsy. The mean age of the participants was 36.8 ± 1.7 years, with those having generalized epilepsy averaging 36.5 ± 1.7 years and those with focal epilepsy averaging 37.4 ± 1.5 years (P value: 0.458).

In terms of gender distribution, 64% of the participants were male, with 65% in the generalized epilepsy group and 62% in the focal epilepsy group,

while females accounted for 36% of the total population (P value: 0.652). The mean age of seizure onset was 26.1 ± 1.3 years overall, with generalized epilepsy cases starting at 24.3 ± 1.2 years and focal epilepsy at 25.5 ± 1.4 years (P value: 0.721). The average duration of epilepsy was 12.5 ± 2.3 years, with similar durations for both generalized (12.4 ± 2.1 years) and focal epilepsy (12.8 ± 2.4 years) groups (P value: 0.623). The duration of epilepsy was less than 5 years in 42% of participants, between 5 to 10 years in 39%, and more than 10 years

in 19%, with similar distributions across both epilepsy types (P value: 0.733).

Discussion:

The study examined various clinical variables among 250 participants, with 147 (59%) diagnosed with generalized epilepsy and 103 (47%) with focal epilepsy. Drug compliance was present in 68% of the participants, with 67% in the generalized epilepsy group and 68% in the focal epilepsy group, while 32% were non-compliant with their medication (P value: 0.711). Regarding seizure control, 56% of the participants had controlled seizures, with similar proportions in both generalized (55%) and focal (56%) epilepsy groups, and 44% had uncontrolled seizures (P value: 0.678). When considering drug treatment, 43% of the participants were on monotherapy, with 42% in the generalized group and 44% in the focal group, while 57% were on polytherapy (P value: 0.721). MRI abnormalities were present in 23% of the participants, with a significantly higher prevalence in the focal epilepsy group (31%) compared to the generalized group (17%) (P value: 0.031). EEG changes were observed in 33% of the participants, with a higher incidence in the focal epilepsy group (41%) than in the generalized group (28%) (P value: 0.001).

Table 3 shows the scores from the Indian semantic memory test battery, indicating the percentage of the population scoring less than 50% in various categories. For the total naming score, 10% of individuals with generalized epilepsy and 12% with focal epilepsy scored below 50%, resulting in an overall rate of 11%. In the total word-picture matching score, 14% of those with generalized epilepsy and 16% of those with focal epilepsy scored under 50%, with a combined rate of 15%. For picture sorting level 1, 13% of the generalized epilepsy group and 14% of the focal epilepsy group scored below 50%, with a total of 12.5%. In word sorting level 1, 10.5% of the generalized epilepsy group and 12.4% of the focal epilepsy group scored below 50%, resulting in an overall rate of 11.6%. At picture sorting level 2, 12.5% of individuals with generalized epilepsy and 13.4% with focal epilepsy scored under 50%, totaling 13.2%. For word sorting level 2, 14.3% of the generalized group and 15.4% of the focal group scored below 50%, with a combined rate of 14.5%. At picture sorting level 3, 21.5% of those with generalized epilepsy and 24.4% with focal epilepsy scored below 50%, resulting in an overall rate of 23.6%. Finally, in word sorting level 3, 23.3% of the generalized epilepsy group and 25.3% of the focal epilepsy group scored under 50%, with a total of 22.6%.

Christine et al. investigated semantic memory functions—such as word-picture matching, word definition, confrontation and responsive naming,

and word list generation—in 19 patients with temporal lobe epilepsy due to mesial temporal sclerosis (MTS), comparing them to normal controls. Patients with left MTS (LMTS) exhibited poorer performance in word definition (compared to controls and right MTS patients) and in responsive naming (compared to controls). Both RMTS and LMTS groups showed deficits in word-picture matching relative to controls. Additionally, patients with either left or right MTS performed worse than controls on word list generation and confrontation naming tasks. [10] Piazzini et al. found that older individuals with focal epilepsy performed worse on cognitive tests compared to controls, with the number of antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) being associated with greater cognitive impairment. [11]

Similarly, Helene et al. compared cognitive impairments between patients with focal and generalized epilepsy and control groups. They assessed various cognitive domains, including episodic long-term memory, executive function, attention, working memory, visuospatial skills, and language. Both epilepsy groups demonstrated poorer results compared to controls, with the number of convulsive seizures being predictive of episodic long-term memory function. Additionally, participants with focal epilepsy reported a lower quality of life compared to those with generalized epilepsy, consistent with findings from our study. [12]

Conclusion

Our research revealed that cognitive difficulties in patients with epilepsy extend beyond verbal episodic memory impairment, also affecting the semantic-verbal system. These deficits influence both memory and language performance, highlighting an often overlooked aspect of cognitive dysfunction in epilepsy. It is important to differentiate between impairment in the semantic-verbal system and those typically associated with verbal episodic memory. Since the semantic-verbal system plays a crucial role in supporting knowledge, its impairment can also negatively impact the verbal episodic memory system.

Epilepsy is increasingly recognized as a complex neurobehavioral disorder. A deeper understanding of the semantic processing challenges faced by these patients will enhance our insight into the language and memory difficulties they experience, particularly in both declarative memory subsystems—semantic and episodic. This understanding is key to improving care and support for individuals with epilepsy.

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